

Refining polyploid breeding in sweetpotato through allele dosage enhancement

Xiangbo Zhang^{1,9}, Chaochen Tang^{1,9}, Bingzhi Jiang^{1,9}, Rong Zhang^{1,9}, Ming Li^{2,3,9}, Yaoyao Wu⁴, Zhufang Yao¹, Lifei Huang¹, Zhongxia Luo¹, Hongda Zou¹, Yiling Yang¹, Minyi Wu⁵, Ao Chen⁵, Shan Wu⁶, Xingliang Hou⁵, Xu Liu^{5,*}, Zhangjun Fei^{6,7,*}, Junjie Fu^{8,*}, Zhangying Wang^{1,*}

¹Crops Research Institute, Guangdong Academy of Agricultural Sciences & Key Laboratory of Crop Genetic Improvement of Guangdong Province, Guangzhou, China

²College of life Sciences, Chongqing Normal University, Chongqing, China

³Institute of Biotechnology and Nuclear Technology, Sichuan Academy of Agricultural Sciences, Chengdu, Sichuan, China

⁴College of Horticulture, Nanjing Agricultural University, Nanjing, China

⁵Guangdong Provincial Key Laboratory of Applied Botany, and State Key Laboratory of Plant Diversity and Specialty Crops, South China Botanical Garden, Chinese Academy of Sciences, Guangzhou, China

⁶Boyce Thompson Institute, Cornell University, Ithaca, NY, USA

⁷USDA-ARS, Robert W. Holley Center for Agriculture and Health, Ithaca, NY, USA

⁸State Key Laboratory of Crop Gene Resources and Breeding, Institute of Crop Sciences, Chinese Academy of Agricultural Sciences, Beijing, China

⁹These authors contributed equally

*Email: liuxu@scbg.ac.cn; zf25@cornell.edu; fujunjie@caas.cn; wangzhangying@gdaas.cn

Abstract

Allele dosage plays a key role in phenotypic variation of polyploids. Here we present a genome-wide variation map of hexaploid sweetpotato that captures allele dosage information, constructed from deep sequencing of 294 hexaploid accessions. Genome-wide association studies identified quantitative trait loci with dosage effects on 23 agronomic traits. Our analyses reveal that sweetpotato breeding has progressively increased the dosage of favorable alleles to enhance trait performance. Notably, the Mesoamerican gene pool has evolved toward higher dosages of favorable alleles at multiple loci, which have been increasingly introgressed into modern Chinese cultivars. We substantiated the breeding-driven dosage accumulation through transgenic validation of *IbEXPA4*, an expansin gene influencing tuberous root weight. Additionally, we explored causative sequence variations that alter the expression of the *Orange* gene, which regulates flesh color. Our findings illuminate the breeding history of sweetpotato and establish a foundation for leveraging allele dosages in polyploid breeding practices.

Introduction

Approximately 40% of cultivated plant species are polyploid¹, a characteristic driven by whole-genome duplications (WGDs) and central to the origin and evolution of most crop species²⁻⁵. Compared to their diploid counterparts, polyploids typically exhibit enhanced growth vigor and a broader geographic distribution, reflecting the increased phenotypic variation enabled by multiple alleles in their homoeologous chromosomes⁶. Genome-wide gene expression studies in polyploids have revealed both additive and nonadditive dosage effects on gene expression⁷⁻⁹. For instance, the proportion of expressed genes with additive effect ranges from 65% to 95% in Arabidopsis allotetraploids, while that with nonadditive effect varies from 5% to 38%^{10,11}. In hexaploid *Camelina sativa*, the additive effect of allele dosage at the *FAD2* loci on seed oleic acid profile has been demonstrated in CRISPR-Cas9 edited lines¹². To date, dosage effects have primarily been studied at the gene expression level and on several cloned genes. However, the connection between allele dosage and agronomic traits in large populations remains poorly understood and presents a promising avenue for further trait improvement.

Recent research has advanced crop breeding by identifying superior alleles, as seen in maize (*Zea mays ssp. mays* L.), rice (*Oryza sativa*), common bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris* L.), and wheat (*Triticum aestivum*)¹³⁻¹⁸. However, previous population genetic studies in polyploids have employed a simplified approach, treating polyploids as diploids for variant calling and population genetic analyses¹⁹⁻²¹, which has led to the omission of information on heterozygous loci and inaccurate estimation of allele dosage effects. With the advances of sequencing technologies and computational algorithms, it is now possible to predict allele dosage and assess its effects on phenotypic variation in polyploids. Furthermore, a comprehensive genome-wide scan of breeding footprints in polyploids to identify and evaluate allele dosage in the breeding process would provide crucial insights for crop improvement.

Sweetpotato [*Ipomoea batatas* (L.) Lam.] is a globally important food crop, with an annual production of approximately 86.4 million tons in 2022 (FAOSTAT; <http://faostat.fao.org/>). China is the world's largest producer and consumer of sweetpotato, accounting for ~54% of the global

production. Given the hexaploid nature of sweetpotato, exploring genetic variants with dosage effects and understanding their roles in sweetpotato breeding is critical. In this study, we deep-sequenced 294 sweetpotato accessions and systematically investigated the selection of agronomic traits during sweetpotato breeding, the population structure of these accessions, and the involvement of allele dosage in sweetpotato breeding. We identified genome regions with allele dosage effects on 23 agronomic traits and conducted transgenic confirmation for candidate genes/variations related to tuberous root weight and flesh color. This study highlights the importance of allele dosage in influencing agronomic traits and provides valuable resources of superior alleles to accelerate sweetpotato breeding efforts.

Results

Phenotypic evolution during sweetpotato breeding

To analyze the impact of allele dosage on phenotypic variation and polyploid sweetpotato breeding, we collected 294 accessions spanning different stages along the sweetpotato breeding history (**Supplementary Table 1**). This collection comprised 250 accessions from China, as well as 44 from other countries that have been frequently used as donors in sweetpotato breeding in China. Of the 250 accessions from China, 135 were landraces and 115 were cultivars (**Fig. 1a** and **Supplementary Table 1**). The 115 Chinese cultivars were further divided into two groups based on distinct breeding targets²², i.e., 51 early-stage cultivars released before 2000 with white/light-yellow flesh color (denoted as B2000) and 64 recent cultivars released after 2000 with purple/orange flesh color (denoted as A2000).

To elucidate the improvement characteristics of sweetpotato, 23 agronomic traits were investigated in these 294 accessions grown in Guangzhou, China, in 2020 and 2021 (**Extended Data Fig. 1** and **Supplementary Table 2**). Principal component analysis (PCA) of the phenotypic data for these traits largely separated the B2000 and A2000 cultivars (**Extended Data Fig. 2**), further supporting the classification of Chinese cultivars into these two groups. Of the 23 traits, 17 (73.91%) showed improvement during sweetpotato breeding, including five tuberous root weight traits, four tuberous root appearance traits, one flesh color trait, six high-density planting traits,

and the leaf shape trait (**Fig. 1b-e** and **Extended Data Fig. 3**). Tuberous root production, the primary target for sweetpotato improvement, is determined by a combination of planting density and tuberous root weight. We observed that plant architecture traits were preferentially selected from landrace to B2000 (early stage), including more erect branches, shorter internode length, lower ground fresh weight, shorter vine length, and more compact tuberous roots, which together contribute to increased plant density tolerance (**Fig. 1b**). Tuberous root weight (per individual) was preferentially selected from B2000 to A2000 (later stage) (**Fig. 1c**). Consequently, the increase in total tuberous root production reflected a shift from high-density planting to a combination of high-density planting and increased tuberous root weight (**Fig. 1f**). Notably, tuberous root appearance was preferentially selected after the 2000s due to consumer preference, with favored traits including purple skin color, smooth tuberous root surface, spindle-shaped tuberous roots, and orange flesh color (**Fig. 1d,e**). In summary, sweetpotato breeding has resulted in increased tuberous root weight, improved tuberous root appearance, higher flesh quality, and better adaptation to high planting density.

Population structure and genetic diversity

To construct a genome-wide variation map of hexaploid sweetpotato that captures allele dosage information, we deep-sequenced these 294 accessions at an average depth of 26.2× per haplotype, equivalent to 157× relative to the monoploid genome of hexaploid sweetpotato (**Supplementary Table 1**). The high-quality reads were mapped to the genome assembly of the wild diploid *I. trifida*, which has been reported to be a robust reference for hexaploid sweetpotato²³ (available at <https://ngdc.cncb.ac.cn>; accession number PRJCA015454). The mapping rates ranged from 98.1% to 99.5%, allowing us to accurately identify full hexaploid genotypes with allele dosage, as described in a previous study²⁴. Using GATK²⁵, we generated a final set of 6,828,068 single-nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) and 1,679,020 small insertions or deletions (indels) (**Supplementary Table 3** and **Supplementary Fig. 1**). Of these SNPs, approximately 7.38% were located in coding regions (**Supplementary Fig. 2**), with 3.14% and 0.06% annotated as missense

and stop-gain variations, respectively (**Supplementary Table 4**). SNP distribution varied across chromosomes, exhibiting a profile similar to that of gene density (**Supplementary Fig. 1**). Within this SNP set, we calculated the percentages of SNPs with three different dosages: simplex (single dose), duplex and triplex. Simplex SNPs were the predominant type, with an average of 54.1% in each accession, while duplex and triplex SNPs represented 33.0% and 12.9%, respectively (**Supplementary Fig. 3**).

We performed phylogenetic analysis to provide a better understanding of the history of sweetpotato breeding, which revealed that accessions from outside China sporadically clustered with landraces and cultivars from China, consistent with the frequent usage of germplasms from other regions as donors in sweetpotato breeding in China (**Fig. 2a**). Furthermore, population structure and PCA uncovered three distinct ancestry components (optimal $K=3$), corresponding to the Peruvian-Ecuadorian, Colombian-Venezuelan, and Mesoamerican gene pools identified in a previous study that analyzed 5,792 sweetpotato accessions in the CIP sweetpotato germplasm collection using simple sequence repeat (SSR) markers²⁶ (**Fig. 2b**, **Extended Data Fig. 4** and **Supplementary Figs. 4,5**). The Peruvian-Ecuadorian and Mesoamerican gene pools contained representative accessions Okinanwa100 from Japan and Nancy Hall from USA, respectively, consistent with the previous finding that these two accessions clustered with those from Peru and Ecuador and Mesoamerica in the CIP sweetpotato germplasm collection²⁶. Accessions in the Colombian-Venezuelan gene pool exhibited genetic admixture with the Peruvian-Ecuadorian and Mesoamerican gene pools at $K=2$, both in this study and in the CIP collection²⁶. We found that the Mesoamerican gene pool showed a lower genetic differentiation from the Colombian-Venezuelan gene pool ($F_{ST}=0.04181$) than from the Peruvian-Ecuadorian gene pool ($F_{ST}=0.06399$) (**Fig. 2c**), and that the Colombian-Venezuelan gene pool displayed intermediate phenotypic traits that were further improved in the Mesoamerican gene pool (**Extended Data Fig. 5**). Therefore, we hypothesize that the Colombian-Venezuelan gene pool may have originated from the Peruvian-Ecuadorian gene pool (primitive gene pool) and evolved into the Mesoamerican gene pool (improved gene pool).

Admixture due to inter-gene pool introgression was observed in the ‘Mixed’ subpopulation, which contained ancestry components from all three gene pools (**Fig. 2b**). This subpopulation included 66 landraces and 74 cultivars, suggesting that these landraces could be close ancestors used for sweetpotato breeding in China. As expected, the improved gene pool (Mesoamerican) represented the predominant ancestry component in the cultivars (52.7%), while the primitive gene pool (Peruvian-Ecuadorian) and the intermediate gene pool (Colombian-Venezuelan) represented 16.0% and 31.3%, respectively (**Fig. 2d**). Moreover, the component of the improved Mesoamerican gene pool in cultivars gradually expanded during sweetpotato breeding (**Fig. 2e**). These results suggest that the Mesoamerican gene pool played a major role in sweetpotato breeding in China.

Finally, we observed a modest reduction in genetic diversity during sweetpotato breeding. The genetic diversity (expected heterozygosity; H_S) of landraces (8.471×10^{-3}) was significantly higher than that of B2000 (8.407×10^{-3}), while no significant difference was observed between B2000 and A2000 (8.402×10^{-3}). Overall, cultivars retained 99.2% of the genetic diversity compared to landraces, suggesting a weak bottleneck during sweetpotato improvement.

Capturing QTLs with dosage effects

We next conducted genome-wide association studies (GWAS) using SNP dosage data with GWASpoly²⁷, to identify QTLs with allele dosage effects on 23 agronomic traits and to evaluate their contributions to phenotypic variation and breeding. We identified a total of 650 unique QTLs significantly associated with traits measured over two independent years (2020 and 2021), along with their best linear unbiased predictor (BLUP) values (**Supplementary Table 5** and **Supplementary Fig. 6**). Of these, 353 QTLs were associated with the BLUP phenotypic values. These 353 QTLs typically spanned less than 200 kb and encompassed 6,938 genes (**Supplementary Table 6** and **Supplementary Fig. 7**). Among these genes, 1,488 harbored SNPs annotated as missense or stop-gain variations, as well as those located within 5 kb upstream and downstream regions of the genes. The lead SNPs within these QTLs exhibited dosage effects on

phenotypic variation, indicating that changes in allele dosage were associated with proportional changes in phenotypes (**Fig. 3a** and **Supplementary Table 7**). Notably, accessions with heterozygous genotypes exhibited intermediate phenotypes compared to those with either of the two homozygous genotypes (**Extended Data Fig. 6**). The additive effects of these QTLs substantially contributed to trait variation in sweetpotato, with the phenotypic variance explained (PVE) by all lead SNPs for each trait ranging from 59.60% to 75.23%, e.g., 72.58% for tuberous root weight and 72.64% for flesh color (**Supplementary Fig. 8**). Among the 353 QTLs, 68 (19.2%) had PVE values greater than 10%, highlighting their potential as valuable genetic resources for molecular-assisted breeding (**Supplementary Table 8**).

We revisited several previously reported QTLs and cloned genes and found that they appeared to function in a dosage-dependent manner. Four QTLs identified in our study have been previously reported²⁸, including those associated with both overground traits (internode length and leaf shape) and underground traits (flesh color and tuberous root weight) (**Supplementary Table 9**). Previously identified genes, such as *IbMYB1*²⁹ associated with skin color and *IbFBOX*^{28,30} associated with leaf shape, were found within GWAS signals (**Fig. 3b,c**). Additionally, we identified several plausible candidate genes. The QTLs for flesh color on chromosomes 1, 7, and 11 contained *IbCCD4*, *IbPSY*, and *IbOr*, which are homologous to Arabidopsis *CCD4*³¹ and *PSY*³², and cauliflower (*Brassica oleracea* var. *botrytis*) *Or*³³, respectively (**Fig. 3d** and **Supplementary Table 10**). The QTL associated with tuberous root weight on chromosome 2 included an expansin gene, *IbEXPA4*, potentially involved in cell wall loosening and cell enlargement³⁴ (**Fig. 3e**). A correlation between different allele dosages and their corresponding phenotypes was consistent with these genes functioning in a dosage-dependent manner (**Fig. 3f**).

Contribution of gene pools to favorable allele accumulation

The Mesoamerican gene pool exhibited improved agronomic traits compared to the Colombian-Venezuelan and Peruvian-Ecuadorian gene pools (**Extended Data Fig. 5**). To investigate whether this improvement involves dosage accumulation of favorable alleles (defined as those positively

associated with desirable traits such as higher tuberous root weight, increased planting density, and improved tuberous root appearance, based on lead SNPs in QTL intervals), we focused on nine major genomic loci associated with high planting density traits, tuberous root weight, and flesh color and analyzed the distribution of different favorable allele dosages across accessions with varying compositions of the three gene pools. This analysis revealed that high-dosage favorable alleles for these nine QTLs were mainly contributed by the Colombian-Venezuelan and/or the Mesoamerican gene pool (**Fig. 4a**). Specifically, high-dosage favorable alleles for five of the nine QTLs were primarily contributed by the Mesoamerican gene pool, three by the Colombian-Venezuelan gene pool, and one by both. These findings support the hypothesis that sweetpotato improvement involved dosage accumulation of favorable alleles primarily contributed by the Mesoamerican gene pool.

Tuberous root weight is a key target in sweetpotato breeding. We identified two significantly associated genomic loci carrying high-dosage favorable alleles: one primarily contributed by the Mesoamerican gene pool (*Chr2_3326986*) and another by the Colombian-Venezuelan gene pool (*Chr10_20914146*) (**Fig. 4a**). This suggests the frequent utilization of these two gene pools in sweetpotato breeding programs to increase tuberous root weight. The Mesoamerican gene pool, represented by Nancy Hall, also carried valuable genetic potential for flesh color improvement, as it contained three major genomic loci with high-dosage favorable alleles for this trait (**Fig. 4a**). This finding aligns with that Nancy Hall possessed a relatively high number of favorable alleles associated with flesh color among the 294 accessions (**Supplementary Fig. 9**). Finally, we found that the enhancement of cultivars with more erect branches could be achieved by introducing the high-dosage favorable allele (*Chr7_4547410*) from the Colombian-Venezuelan gene pool (**Fig. 4a**). Our findings highlight the contributions of the Mesoamerican and Colombian-Venezuelan gene pools, each providing specific high-dosage favorable alleles to the improved traits in modern sweetpotato (**Fig. 4b**).

Leveraging dosage of favorable alleles to enhance breeding

Sweetpotato breeding has historically focused on selecting accessions with favorable agronomic traits, progressively refining these traits through continuous breeding cycles (**Fig. 1f**). Comprehensive understanding of the impact of allele dosage on breeding provides valuable insights for further trait improvement. To assess allele dosage effects along sweetpotato breeding, we quantified their accumulation among landraces, and B2000 and A2000 cultivars. Our analysis revealed a dosage accumulation of favorable alleles over the breeding process, although this dosage accumulation was modest (average allele dosage accumulation of <1) (**Fig. 5a** and **Extended Data Fig. 7**), indicating that small allele dosage changes likely contribute to improvements of tuberous root and plant architecture traits. Pedigree-based analysis provided further insights into favorable allele accumulation in sweetpotato breeding. For example, analyzing the pedigrees of Guangshu87 and Longshu9 (both released after 2000 and exhibiting high tuberous root weight), containing three and five accessions sequenced in this study, respectively, revealed the accumulation of favorable alleles across multiple tuberous root traits during their breeding (**Fig. 5b-e**). These results suggest that allele dosage accumulation, both at single and multiple loci, has empowered sweetpotato breeding.

The presence of undesirable traits can hinder the market release of cultivars. The identification of favorable alleles offers new insights into genome design for precisely selecting appropriate donor parents and improving these traits. We quantified the accumulated favorable alleles in each of the 294 sweetpotato accessions. For instance, we selected nine widely planted cultivars and assessed the genomic scores (accumulated favorable alleles) of 15 improved agronomic traits (**Fig. 5f** and **Supplementary Table 11**). Notably, Guangshu87, Pushu32 and Yanshu25, which are widely planted in China and have highly valued tuberous root and non-tuberous root traits, carried relatively more favorable alleles compared to other accessions (**Fig. 5f**). However, some cultivars showed less accumulated favorable alleles for a few traits. For example, Jishu26, a cultivar carrying relatively high number of accumulated favorable alleles, accumulated less favorable alleles for vine length (63 accumulated in Jishu26 compared to the highest of 87 in Jieshu95) and branching angle (35 compared to the highest of 75 in Zi14-76),

which can affect field management and planting density (**Fig. 5f**). Therefore, Jieshu95 and Zi14-76 could serve as donor parents to improve these two traits in Jishu26 through backcrossing, targeting the identified favorable allele sites (**Supplementary Fig. 10**). Consequently, the dosage information for identified favorable alleles across different sweetpotato accessions has the potential to support further trait improvement efforts.

Both tuberous root weight and high-density planting traits are important contributors to tuberous root production, and identification of underlying regulatory genes is critical for sweetpotato improvement. We analyzed five major QTLs associated with these traits and compared their genotype frequencies from landraces to cultivars. We observed that cultivars had a higher frequency of homozygous favorable alleles than landraces, while the frequency of heterozygous genotypes with five copies of favorable alleles was lower (**Extended Data Fig. 8**). Consequently, genotypes with high-dosage favorable alleles were gradually accumulated in sweetpotato breeding. We next identified putative causal genes in these QTL regions (**Extended Data Fig. 8** and **Supplementary Table 6**). The major QTL *Chr7_4547410* for branching angle contained two adjacent genes encoding cytochrome P450 CYP2 proteins (*IbCYP84A1-1* and *IbCYP84A1-2*), which are homologous to rice *D2*, known for regulating tiller angle^{35,36}. QTL *Chr4_28111667* for vine length contained *IbERF02*, encoding an ethylene-responsive transcription factor and homologous to Arabidopsis *ERF02* that is known to be involved in regulating plant growth via hindering auxin accumulation³⁷. QTL *Chr14_784778* associated with overground fresh weight contained two adjacent genes encoding auxin efflux carriers (*IbPIN5-1* and *IbPIN5-2*), with *IbPIN5-1* upregulated during early stem development (**Supplementary Fig. 11**), further supporting its role in auxin transport related to overground fresh weight. QTL *Chr4_22571183* for tuberous root compactness contained an auxin-responsive protein gene (*IbARF*), consistent with the function of its homolog in maize in regulating root angle³⁸. These candidate genes provide important resources for sweetpotato trait improvement.

Validation of genes influencing tuberous root traits

Genetic variants with dosage effects, identified by GWAS in this study, have facilitated the discovery of candidate causative variants and functional genes. To functionally confirm these candidate genes/variants, we focused on tuberous root weight and flesh color, two of the most important yield and quality traits for sweetpotato breeding.

As outlined above, a major QTL associated with tuberous root weight on chromosome 2 was found to harbor an expansin gene, *IbEXPA4* (**Figs. 3e and 6a**), whose homologs are known to contribute to cell enlargement. The favorable allele of a significant SNP near *IbEXPA4* has been selectively chosen during sweetpotato breeding (**Supplementary Fig. 12a**). The expression of *IbEXPA4* showed a negative correlation with the dosage of the favorable allele, indicating that the favorable allele enhances tuberous root weight by suppressing *IbEXPA4* expression in a dosage-dependent manner (**Fig. 6b,c**). To confirm its role in root development, three independent overexpressing and two independent RNA interference (RNAi) transgenic lines of *IbEXPA4* were generated in sweetpotato. The *IbEXPA4*-overexpressing lines exhibited increased root lignification and negatively regulated tuberous root expansion, while the *IbEXPA4*-RNAi lines accelerated tuberous root formation (**Fig. 6d-f and Extended Data Fig. 9**), further confirming the functional role of *IbEXPA4* in negatively regulating tuberous root enlargement. Additionally, we conducted RNA-Seq on tuberous roots of *IbEXPA4*-overexpressing and wild-type plants to investigate the biological processes potentially regulated by *IbEXPA4* (**Supplementary Table 12**). A total of 4,651 differentially expressed genes (DEGs) were identified (**Extended Data Fig. 10a and Supplementary Table 13**). Gene ontology (GO) term analysis revealed that these DEGs were significantly enriched with those in hormone related pathways, as well as those involved in lignin metabolism, cell wall organization, and cell division (**Extended Data Fig. 10b**). This finding is consistent with the reported functions of expansin proteins, which loosen the cell wall by unlocking the network of wall polysaccharides³⁴. Notably, 11 of the 15 DEGs annotated in the lignin biosynthetic process (GO:0009809) were upregulated in *IbEXPA4*-overexpressing plants (**Extended Data Fig. 10b and Supplementary Table 13**), indicating that overexpression of *IbEXPA4* increased lignin content in tuberous roots, thereby suppressing their expansion.

Major QTLs for flesh color were mapped to chromosomes 1, 7, and 11, each containing plausible candidate genes involved in carotenoid metabolism, namely *IbCCD4*, *IbPSY*, and *IbOr* (**Fig. 3d**). Previous studies have reported that the *Or* gene regulates chromoplast biogenesis and enhances β -carotene accumulation^{33,39-41}. In this study, we observed an accumulation of the favorable allele in the promoter of *IbOr* during sweetpotato improvement (**Fig. 6g,h** and **Supplementary Fig. 12b**). The *IbOr* promoters were cloned from an orange-fleshed accession (Nancy Hall) and a light-yellow-fleshed accession (Pengwei), revealing two insertions, a 136-bp insertion (I1) and a 94-bp insertion (I2) located at 998 bp and 1681 bp upstream of the *IbOr* start codon, respectively (**Fig. 6i**). Nancy Hall possessed three haplotypes (I1+I2, I2, and no insertion), while Pengwei had only one haplotype (I1) (**Fig. 6i**). In order to investigate the activities of these four different promoter haplotypes, we conducted the transient expression assays, which revealed that all three haplotypes from Nancy Hall significantly enhanced the expression of the luciferase reporter gene compared to the I1 haplotype from Pengwei (**Fig. 6j**). This suggests a possible dosage effect of the haplotypes from Nancy Hall on *IbOr* expression.

Discussion

This study involves deep sequencing and phenotyping of a broad collection of sweetpotato accessions, encompassing both core germplasm and accessions along the sweetpotato breeding history, covering three gene pools that have been extensively used in sweetpotato breeding. This comprehensive approach allowed us to construct a detailed variation map that captures allele dosage information, shedding light on the impact of allele dosages on phenotype variation and breeding in polyploid sweetpotato. Our findings reveal that the sweetpotato genome contains numerous loci associated with important agronomical traits in a dosage-dependent manner, and that the effect of allele dosage has substantially contributed to phenotypic variation, providing valuable information to facilitate the design of effective sweetpotato breeding strategies that involve adjusting the allele dosages at specific loci and pyramiding multiple loci.

By employing this variation map, we addressed the limitations of standard analytical

approaches that are typically applied to diploid crops but often fall short in polyploids. These standard approaches, which simplify polyploid heterozygous states to only two states, can lead to inaccuracies in analyses such as PCA, phylogeny, population structure, nucleotide diversity, and GWAS. Similar issues are highlighted in a previous population genetics analysis of autotetraploid alfalfa (*Medicago sativa*)²¹. Previous diploid-based approaches applied to sweetpotato in analyzing the associated genomic loci of various traits proved to be inadequate for detecting the dosage effect of alleles⁴². Furthermore, it has been demonstrated that accounting for allele dosage can enhance genomic selection in highly polyploid species characterized by a higher frequency of different heterozygous genotypic classes⁴³. Therefore, constructing a variation map that captures allele dosage information is critical for studying polyploid genetics.

Sweetpotato, being clonally propagated, often exhibits heterozygous genotypes with phenotypes that may differ from their parents, indicating the presence of both additive and nonadditive effects of alleles⁴⁴. In clonally propagated polyploids, both gene actions are transmitted across breeding generations⁴⁵. Our study revealed that heterozygous genotypes exhibited an intermediate phenotypic effect compared to the two types of homozygous genotypes (additive effect), while the allele interaction (nonadditive effect) was not observed (**Extended Data Fig. 6**). Furthermore, our study demonstrates that the additive effect of allele dosage played a substantial role in sweetpotato phenotypic variation, highlighting the primary influence of additive action over nonadditive action. The additive model can result in a broader range of intermediate phenotypes, some of which may confer selective advantages⁴⁶. Identification of genomic loci with dosage-dependent phenotype regulation provides valuable information for sweetpotato improvement, as exemplified by a major locus on chromosome 11 associated with skin color, where allele dosage changes result in a spectrum of phenotypes ranging from white to purple. The relationship between allele/gene dosage and phenotype has been explored in targeted mutagenesis studies, such as the *FAD2* gene in the hexaploid oilseed crop *Camelina sativa*, manipulation of which resulted in more intermediate phenotypes and demonstrated an additive dosage correlation with lipid profiles¹². However, it remains largely unexplored how sequence

variants affect phenotypes in a dosage-dependent manner in polyploids. Our large association population provided an ideal platform for investigating how genes participate in dosage-phenotype regulation. Analysis of *IbEXPA4*, a candidate gene associated with tuberous root weight, revealed a negative correlation between the dosage of the favorable allele and gene expression. This enabled us to establish a three-way connection among favorable allele dosages, gene expression, and phenotypic traits.

Tracing changes in favorable allele dosages during sweetpotato breeding provides valuable knowledge for guiding future crop improvement^{13,47}. However, unlike diploid crops, hexaploid sweetpotato comprises seven genotype classes for each locus with allele dosages ranging from 0 to 6. Our findings indicate a gradual increase of favorable allele dosages during sweetpotato improvement, with an average accumulation of 0.8 favorable allele copies associated with tuberous root weight for each QTL in modern cultivars compared to the primitive gene pool. This suggests that sweetpotato breeding could benefit from utilizing allele dosage more effectively. Moreover, existing favorable alleles have not been fully exploited, particularly in regions like China with less intensive breeding practices in sweetpotato. We propose a strategy based on assessing the accumulation of favorable alleles to improve accessions with fewer accumulated favorable alleles for certain traits by targeting trait-associated QTLs through backcrossing with donor parents that have a higher accumulation of favorable alleles for these traits. Additionally, utilizing the identified favorable alleles, traits in accessions can be improved by applying advanced techniques such as genomic selection and genome editing. This study, therefore, provides valuable insights for guiding trait improvement in polyploid species.

Methods

Plant material and phenotyping

From a total of 1,091 sweetpotato accessions preserved in the National Sweetpotato Germplasm Nursery (Guangzhou, China), we constructed a core collection comprising 250 landraces and cultivars from China, as well as 44 accessions from other countries frequently used as breeding parents in China⁴⁸. The cultivars were divided into two groups: those released before 2000 (B2000)

and those released after 2000 (A2000), reflecting the shift in the focus of sweetpotato breeding in China from processing to fresh-eating around the year 2000. A two-year field experiment was conducted for this core collection at the Baiyun Experimental Station (23°23'N, 113°26'E) of the Guangdong Academy of Agricultural Sciences in 2020 and 2021, using a randomized complete block design with three replicates. Each plot (4.4 m²) consisted of two rows (2 m long in the North-South direction), with a plant spacing of 20 cm and a row spacing of 110 cm. A total of 23 agronomic traits were investigated, and the phenotype descriptors were adopted from the “Specifications and Data Standards for the Description of Sweetpotato Germplasm Resources” and “Morphological identification of duplicates in collections of *Ipomoea batatas*”^{49,50}, which provides illustrative graphs of both above- and under-ground traits to assist in classifying these traits into different categorical values. Detailed descriptions of these traits are provided in the Supplementary Note.

To eliminate environmental deviations and obtain the true genetic effect of phenotypic values, phenotypic values for the 23 traits across all trials were adjusted using the best linear unbiased prediction (BLUP) method. The lme4 package (v1.1-35.5) in R was used to calculate the BLUP values for each trait (phenotypes ~ (1|year) + (1|lines) + (1|year:lines) + (1|year:replicate)). Pairwise comparisons of the trait values were conducted using Student's *t*-test with the 'stat_compare_means' function in the R package ggplot2 (v3.5.1).

Genome sequencing and SNP calling

Young fresh leaves from the 294 sweetpotato accessions were sampled, and genomic DNA was extracted using the cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB) method. The extracted DNA was then fragmented by ultrasound on a Covaris E220 (Covaris, Brighton, UK), and fragments ranging from 300 to 500 bp were selected using magnetic bead size selection. For each of the 294 accessions, a sequencing library was constructed using the MGleasy Kit (BGI) following the manufacturer's recommendations. Briefly, the selected DNA fragments were repaired to create blunt ends and modified at the 3'-end to generate dATP sticky ends. The dTTP-tailed adaptor was ligated to both ends of the DNA fragments, which were then amplified by PCR and circularized to obtain a single-stranded circular (ssCir) library. The ssCir library was then amplified through

rolling circle amplification to obtain DNA nanoballs (DNBs). These DNBs were loaded onto a flow cell and sequenced using the DNBSEQ Platform.

Raw reads were processed to remove adaptor and low-quality sequences using Trimmomatic⁵¹ (v0.39). The cleaned reads were subsequently mapped to the *I. trifida* genome (<https://ngdc.cncb.ac.cn>; accession number PRJCA015454) using BWA-MEM (v0.7.17) with default parameters⁵². The resulting SAM files were converted to BAM files using SAMtools⁵³ (v1.9), which were sorted according to the physical position of read alignments on the genome. Duplicated reads in the sorted BAM files were marked using the MarkDuplicates command in GATK²⁵ (v4.2.2.0). The HaplotypeCaller function in GATK was employed to call SNPs for each accession with the parameters ‘--sample-ploidy 6 -ERC GVCF’. The GenomicsDBImport command was used to integrate the gvcf files of individual accessions, and the GenotypeGVCFs tool was used to call SNPs. Raw SNPs were filtered using the VariantFiltration tool with the following parameters: “-filter ‘QD < 2.0’ --filter-name ‘QD2’ -filter ‘QUAL < 30.0’ --filter-name ‘QUAL30’ -filter ‘FS > 60.0’ --filter-name ‘FS60’ -filter ‘MQ < 40.0’ --filter-name ‘MQ40’”. Additional filtering was performed as follows: 1) SNPs with an average read depth > the mean plus two standard deviations were filtered out, as these sites were likely located in repetitive genome regions; 2) Excessive heterozygosity sites (more than 80% of accessions with a heterozygosity rate between 0.33 and 0.67), which could represent potential misassembled regions, were also filtered out; 3) SNPs with lower read coverage (<20×) were defined as missing genotypes; 4) SNPs with a minor allele frequency < 0.05 or a missing rate > 0.5 were filtered out. Finally, a total of 6,828,068 SNPs and 1,679,029 indels were obtained.

Population structure, PCA, and phylogenetic analyses

To infer the ancestry components in the 294 sweetpotato accessions, we conducted a population structure analysis based on spatially explicit Bayesian clustering models for clustering, as implemented in the LEA R package⁵⁴ (v3.8.3).

We performed 100 repetitions for *K* values ranging from 2 to 6 and determined the optimal

K value (3) with the lowest cross-entropy value. Initially, genotypes 0/0/0/0/0, 0/0/0/0/1, 0/0/0/1/1, 0/0/1/1/1, 0/1/1/1/1, 1/1/1/1/1, and missing, where ‘0’ represented the reference allele and ‘1’ represented the alternative allele, were converted to 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, and 9, respectively. The snmf function in LEA was then used to generate a project associated with the genotype file using the parameter ‘ploidy = 6’. We assessed the robustness of the results by running snmf with four values of the α regularization parameter: 10, 50, 100, and 500. Subsequently, the Q function was used to perform the population structure analysis. PCA was performed using the glPCA function implemented in the adegenet package⁵⁵ (v2.2.10).

For phylogenetic tree construction, we randomly selected SNPs from the whole SNP dataset with replacement to generate 1,000 genotype files, which were used to calculate the genetic distance for each pair of accessions using the formula described in a previous study⁵⁶, as implemented in the StAMPP package⁵⁷ (v1.6.3). Genotypes in the input files were coded as dosage values: AAAAAA, AAAAAB, AAAABB, AAABBB, AABBBB, ABBBBB, and BBBBBB. Phylogenetic trees for the 1,000 replicates were constructed using Phylip (v3.697; <https://evolution.genetics.washington.edu/phylip.html>), employing the neighbor-joining method. The consensus module in Phylip was then used to generate the final consensus phylogenetic tree with bootstrap confidence levels. The R package ggtree (v1.4.11; <https://bioconductor.org/packages/release/bioc/html/ggtree.html>) was used to visualize the phylogenetic tree.

Genetic diversity and population fixation index (F_{ST})

Genetic diversity can be estimated using the expected heterozygosity (H_s)⁵⁸. H_s was calculated using the Hs function in the adegenet package⁵⁵ (v2.2.10) with the parameter of ploidy=6. Genotypes in the input file were coded as dosage values ranging from 0 to 6. F_{ST} was calculated using the “stampFst” function in the StAMPP package⁵⁷ (v1.6.3) with parameters of nboots=100, percent=95, and nclusters=50. Genotypes in the input file were coded as dosage values: AAAAAA, AAAAAB, AAAABB, AAABBB, AABBBB, ABBBBB, and BBBBBB.

Genome-wide association studies

GWAS were conducted using SNP dosage data (a minor allele frequency ≥ 0.1 and a missing rate ≤ 0.5) with a linear mixed model that accounted for population structure and relative kinship, as implemented in the R package GWASpoly²⁷ (v2.10). First, the set.K function was used to compute the covariance matrix for the polygenic effect. Subsequently, the GWASpoly function was used to perform GWAS using an ‘additive’ model, where the SNP effect was proportional to the dosage of the minor allele. We used the permutation test to determine the P -value threshold. A total of 1000 permutations and a genome-wide significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$ were used, resulting in a threshold of $P < 10^{-5}$ or $-\log_{10}(P) > 5$. Significant signals were identified by grouping adjacent significant SNPs (within 500 kb) that had a pairwise linkage disequilibrium (LD) $r^2 \geq 0.5$, as calculated using the ldseq⁵⁹ package (v2.1.5) in R. The resulting genomic intervals were further assessed, and those containing fewer than two SNPs with $P < 10^{-5}$ or fewer than 10 SNPs with $P < 10^{-3}$ were filtered out. Candidate genes were identified as those located within the genomic intervals and within 50 kb upstream or downstream of the genomic intervals.

Phenotypic variance explained (PVE) by QTLs

We calculated the PVE for each individual QTL, as well as the total PVE for all QTLs associated with a particular trait, using a previously reported cross-validation approach⁶⁰. A training set consisting of 75% of the sweetpotato accessions and a test set comprising the remaining 25% were randomly selected. The training set was fitted using the mixed linear model⁶¹ implemented in the rrBLUP package (v4.6.3; <http://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/rrBLUP>), and was subsequently used to predict the phenotypic values of the test set. PVE was then calculated using the following formula:

$$\text{PVE} = 1 - \text{var}(y_{\text{test}} - \hat{y}) / \text{var}(y_{\text{test}})$$

where $\text{var}()$ represents the variance, y_{test} is the phenotypic value of the test set, and \hat{y} is the predicted value of the test set.

RNA-Seq analysis

Tuberous root tissues from six-week-old sweetpotato cultivar Guangshu87 and the *IbEXPA4*-overexpression lines, as well as stem tissues from Guangshu87 at 11 different time points, were sampled. Total RNA was extracted from these samples using the Plant RNA kit (Omega Bio-tek) and subsequently used for RNA-Seq library construction and sequencing on the DNBSEQ Platform with the paired-end mode. Two to three biological replicates were conducted for each sample. Raw RNA-Seq reads were processed using Trimmomatic⁵¹ (v0.93) for quality filtering, and the cleaned reads were then mapped to the *I. trifida* genome using STAR⁶² (v2.7.7a). The resulting BAM alignment files were analyzed using featureCounts⁶³ (v1.6.3) to calculate the raw counts of protein-coding genes, which were subsequently normalized to fragments per kilobase of transcript per million mapped fragments (FPKM) values. Genes differentially expressed between the *IbEXPA4*-overexpressing lines and wild-type Guangshu87 plants were identified using DEseq2⁶⁴ (v1.36.0) with a cutoff of false discovery rate (FDR) < 0.05 and $|\log_2(\text{OE/WT})| \geq 1$. GO terms enriched in the differentially expressed genes were identified using the clusterProfiler package⁶⁵ (v4.4.4) with a cutoff of FDR < 0.05.

Gene cloning and transformation

Plasmid construction and transformation were conducted as previously described^{66,67}. Briefly, for *p35S:IbEXPA4-FLAG*, the coding region of *IbEXPA4* was amplified from Guangshu87 and cloned into the modified binary vector p35S:FLAG with the pCambia1300 backbone (Novagen). For the *p35S:IbEXPA4-RNAi* (*IbEXPA4-RNAi*) constructs, the complementary specific sequence of *IbEXPA4* was amplified and cloned into the modified binary vector p35S-RNAi with the pCambia1300 backbone (Novagen). Primers used are listed in **Supplementary Table 14**. For sweetpotato transformation, a single colony of *Agrobacterium tumefaciens* strain AGL1 containing the target binary plasmid was selected and cultured at 28°C for 2 days. The cultures were then collected by centrifugation at 5000 g for 3 min, washed with a wash buffer, and diluted to an optical

density (OD) of 0.5. One ml of the *Agrobacterium* culture was injected into the fresh stem section of Guangshu87 using a syringe, and the stem was then transplanted into soil and selected for hygromycin resistance until tuberization.

Transient expression assay

For the *pIbOR:LUC* construct, promoter sequences (2 kb) of *IbOr* were amplified from Nancy Hall and Pengwei, respectively, and cloned into the Dual-LUC vector (pGreenII 0800-LUC), which contains a *Firefly luciferase* (LUC^{Fly}) reporter. The *Renilla luciferase* (LUC^{Ren}), driven by the *CMV35S* promoter, was used as an internal control. Primers used are listed in **Supplementary Table 14**. Tobacco leaves were transfected and cultured as previously described⁶⁸. The activities of LUC^{Fly} and LUC^{Ren} were quantified using the Dual-LUC Reporter Assay Kit (Promega) according to the manufacturer's instructions. The LUC activity was calculated as the relative activity of LUC^{Fly} / LUC^{Ren} .

Quantitative real-time PCR analysis

Total RNA was extracted using the Plant RNA kit (Omega Bio-tek), and complementary DNA was synthesized using M-MLV reverse transcriptase (Promega). qRT-PCR was performed in triplicate on a Roche LightCycler480 real-time system with the SYBR qPCR mix (Q711-02, Vazyme). *IbTUA* was used as the internal control, and the relative expression levels were normalized to that of *IbTUA*. Primers used for qRT-PCR are listed in **Supplementary Table 14**.

Data availability

Raw genomic sequencing and RNA-Seq reads have been deposited in the National Center for Biotechnology Information BioProject database under the accession number [PRJNA1089346](https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/bioproject/PRJNA1089346) and [PRJNA1151231](https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/bioproject/PRJNA1151231), respectively. The *I. trifida* genome is available at the National Genomics Data Center under accession number [PRJCA015454](https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/bioproject/PRJCA015454).

Code availability

Custom codes used in this study are available on GitHub (<https://github.com/xiangboabc/population-genetics-analysis-of-autopolyploid-species.git>).

Acknowledgements

We thank Xueying Mo and Meixian Zhi for their assistance in growing plants and phenotyping, and Baobao Wang (Chinese Academy of Agricultural Sciences) and Junpeng Shi (Sun Yat-sen University) for critical reading of the manuscript. This work was supported by grants from the National Key R&D Program of China (2019YFD1000701) to Z.W., the Protection and Utilization for Crop Germplasm Resources (NWB014) to Z.W., the earmarked fund of China Agriculture Research System (CARS-10, Sweetpotato) to Z.W., the Special Fund for Scientific Innovation Strategy-construction of High-Level Academy of Agriculture Science (R2022YJ-YB1004) to X.Z., the Innovation Program of the Chinese Academy of Agricultural Sciences to J.F., and the Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation through SweetGAINS (OPP1213329) to Z.F. and RTB Breeding (CGIAR Investment ID1523-BMGF) Projects under a subcontract with the International Potato Center to Z.F.

Author contributions

Z.W., X.Z., C.T., J.F., and Z.F. designed and managed the project. X.Z. conducted bioinformatics analyses. J.F. participated in data analysis. C.T., B.J. and R.Z. performed phenotyping and generated DNA sequencing data. X.H., X.L. M.W., and A.C. carried out the experimental validation of candidate genes. M.L. provided the reference genome of *I. trifida*. Z.Y., H.Z., L.H., Y.Y., and Z.L. participated in material preparation. X.Z. wrote the manuscript. Z.W., J.F., Z.F., C.T., Y.W. and S.W. revised the manuscript.

Competing interests

The authors declared no competing interests.

Figure legends

Figure 1 Phenotypic changes along sweetpotato breeding. **a** Summary of the sequenced sweetpotato accessions. “Introduced” refers to accessions from outside China. Landrace, B2000 (cultivars released before 2000), and A2000 (cultivars released after 2000) represent accessions from the three distinct breeding stages. **b-e** Boxplots showing phenotypic changes during sweetpotato breeding: high planting density traits (tuberous root compactness, vine length, overground flesh weight, internode length, branching angle, and stem diameter) (**b**), tuberous root weight (number and weight of small and medium tuberous roots) (**c**), tuberous root appearance traits (tuberous root shape, surface defect, skin smoothness, and skin color) (**d**), and tuberous root quality traits (orange flesh color) (**e**). Significance tests for continuous trait data were performed using two-sided Student’s *t*-tests. *, ** and *** indicate significant differences at $P < 0.05$, 0.01, and 0.001, respectively. ns, not significant. In each boxplot, the lower and upper bounds indicate the first and third quartiles, respectively, the center line indicates the median, and whiskers represent $1.5\times$ the interquartile range. Sample sizes are displayed above boxplots. **f** Model for tuberous root production improvement during sweetpotato breeding.

Figure 2 Population structure of diverse sweetpotato accessions. **a,b** Phylogenetic tree (**a**) and population structure ($K = 2$ and 3) (**b**) of sweetpotato accessions. The phylogenetic tree was rooted using hexaploid *I. trifida*, a close wild relative of sweetpotato. Bootstrap confidence levels are shown along the tree from the root to the branches, continuing until they reach 100%. Accessions with an ancestry component ≥ 0.65 for a single gene pool at $K = 3$ were assigned to that gene pool, otherwise to the ‘Mixed’ subpopulation. **c** Population differentiation (F_{ST}) between and expected heterozygosity (H_S) of the three gene pools used in sweetpotato breeding. **d** Percentage of the three gene pools in modern cultivars. **e** Percentage of the three gene pools in landraces, B2000, and A2000 cultivars. Statistical significances of differences between groups were assessed using two-sided Student’s *t*-tests. In each boxplot, the lower and upper bounds indicate the first and third quartiles, respectively, the center line indicates the median, and whiskers represent $1.5\times$ the

interquartile range. Sample sizes are displayed above boxplots.

Figure 3 Genome-wide association studies (GWAS) of sweetpotato. **a** Allele dosage effect on phenotypic variation. For each significant GWAS locus, the average phenotypic value was calculated for each of the seven different dosage genotypes of the lead SNP. In the heatmap, gray, purple and orange colors represent missing, low, and high phenotypic values, respectively. QTLs are listed along the x-axis, while the corresponding dosage genotype classes are shown on the y-axis. “a” denotes the allele associated with low phenotype value and “A” denotes the allele associated with high phenotype value. **b-e** Manhattan plots of GWAS for skin color (**b**), leaf shape (**c**), flesh color (**d**), and tuberous root weight (**e**). Dashed horizontal lines indicate the significance threshold of GWAS at $P = 10^{-5}$. Plausible candidate genes are indicated. **f** Distribution of phenotypes in accessions with different genotypes. Letters above the box plots represent significant differences from multiple comparisons at $P < 0.05$ (analysis of variance followed by Duncan’s multiple-comparison test). In each boxplot, the lower and upper bounds indicate the first and third quartiles, respectively, the center line indicates the median, and whiskers represent $1.5 \times$ the interquartile range. Sample sizes are displayed above boxplots.

Figure 4 Contribution of the three gene pools to the accumulation of favorable alleles for sweetpotato trait improvement. **a** Compositions of the three gene pools in accessions with different favorable allele dosages. The x-axis represents genotypes with favorable allele dosages ranging from D0 to D6, corresponding to 0 to 6 favorable alleles. The y-axis indicates the proportion of each gene pool within the accessions, based on the population structure analysis. In each boxplot, the lower and upper bounds indicate the first and third quartiles, respectively, the center line indicates the median, and the whiskers represent $1.5 \times$ the interquartile range. Sample sizes are displayed above boxplots. **b** Summary of the contribution of the three gene pools to sweetpotato trait improvement.

Figure 5 Accumulation of favorable alleles along sweetpotato breeding. **a** Accumulation of favorable alleles in landraces, and B2000 and A2000 cultivars. *, ** and *** indicate significant differences at $P < 0.05$, 0.01, and 0.001, respectively (two-sided paired Student's *t*-test). ns, not significant. In each boxplot, the lower and upper bounds indicate the first and third quartiles, respectively, the center line indicates the median, and whiskers represent 1.5× the interquartile range. Sample sizes are displayed above boxplots. **b** Pedigree information for the sweetpotato cultivar Guangshu87. Red circles indicate sequenced accessions in this study. **c** Accumulation of favorable alleles in the Guangshu87 pedigree. **d** Pedigree information for the sweetpotato cultivar Longshu9. **e** Accumulation of favorable alleles in the Longshu9 pedigree. **f** Number of favorable alleles accumulated in representative cultivars from China. The number of accumulated favorable alleles for each accession was calculated and then normalized to Z-score using the “scale” function in the R package. “*” denotes a normalized Z-score value < -1.2 , indicating undesirable traits in the cultivars.

Figure 6 Functional validation of candidate genes/variants for tuberous root weight and flesh color. **a,g** Local Manhattan plots of loci associated with tuberous root weight (**a**) and flesh color (**g**). Dashed horizontal lines indicate the significance threshold of GWAS at $P = 10^{-5}$. **b,c** Allele dosage effect of the locus around *IbEXPA4* on tuberous root weight (**b**) and the expression of *IbEXPA4* (**c**). In each boxplot, the lower and upper bounds indicate the first and third quartiles, respectively, the center line indicates the median, and whiskers represent 1.5× the interquartile range. Sample sizes are displayed above boxplots. **d** Expression levels of *IbEXPA4* in wild-type (Guangshu87) and three independent *IbEXPA4*-overexpressing (OE) lines. **e** Phenotype of wild-type and *IbEXPA4*-OE lines grown for 4 months under standard laboratory conditions. Arrows indicate lignified storage roots in *IbEXPA4*-OE lines. Scale bar = 5 cm; **f** Root lignification ratios of wild-type and *IbEXPA4*-OE lines, shown as the percentage of lignified roots to total tuberous roots. **h** Significant GWAS signal around the *IbOr* gene. **i** Sequence variations in the *IbOr* promoter between the orange-fleshed sweetpotato variety T044 (Nancy Hall) and the light-yellow-fleshed

variety T171 (Pengwei). **j** Transient expression assay of different *IbOr* promoter activities in tobacco leaves. Luciferase (LUC) served as the promoter activity reporter. Promoter activity is shown as the ratio of *IbOr* promoter-driven LUC activity to the internal reference of REN activity. *pIbOr/T171*, *pIbOr/T044-1*, *pIbOr/T044-2*, *pIbOr/T044-3*: promoters with only the 136-bp insertion, none of the two insertions, only the 94-bp insertion, and both the 94-bp and 136-bp insertions, respectively. In barplots, data are presented as mean \pm SD. Biological replicate numbers are indicated below bars. Significant difference was assessed with two-sided Student's *t*-tests.

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Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 4

Figure 5

Figure 6